

THE ROLE AND FUNCTIONS OF PARALINGUISTIC MEANS IN THE STORIES OF TAKHIR MALIK

Juraeva Mavludakhan Abdulxamid qizi

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute
masters

jurayevamavludaxon6@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7992867>

Annotation: in the process of Speech Communication, paralinguistic means that accompany linguistic units are of particular importance. Paralinguistic tools in the process of communication are considered additional tools involved in communication, they are always recognized as an approach to linguistic tools by the fact that in speech communication they perform tasks such as transmitting certain information, filling in content, compactification and clarification.

Keywords: paralinguistics, linguistic means, nonverbal means, communication, mimic gestures, artistic speech.

Paralinguistic tools that accompany linguistic units are also of great importance in the process of mutual oratory communication between humans. In the process of communication, paralinguistic means are considered additional tools involved in the process of speech communication, which perform such tasks as transmitting certain information that stands on the basis of communicative attitude, filling in its content, clarifying.

In the exchange of information, that is, the conditionality of the participation of the speaker and the listener in the process of communication, in which the participant's communication movement necessarily expresses a certain attitude, with the listener expressing his attitude, paralinguistic means perform several significant tasks as a side field of linguistics. Linguist A. Nurmonov noted, the study of the culture and way of life of one people, as well as in the process of mastering the language perfectly, is also partially visible in the manifestation of paralinguistic means. The recognition of paralinguistics as an integral important branch of linguistics has been studied and researched over the centuries by linguists from different states. Speech and communication are a necessary need for humans, and for this reason, nonverbal gestures, paralinguistic means have an important place for modern linguistics. In Uzbek, a certain opinion, like all languages in the world, is expressed not only by the linguistic way, but also by non-linguistic means, that is, by nonverbal gestures. While the means in question cannot fully express the concept at the level of thought expressed through speech, it is characterized by the fact that in some places it is able to fulfill the main function of speech communication. In particular, such nonverbal means also have a place in the work of art. In order to consider to the reader the purpose of the writer and the extent to which such tools have a place in the process of ensuring that the work is impressive, we aimed to pass through this article an analysis of the paralinguistic tools presented in some stories by the prolific creator, Takhir Malik: the scientist who went Astana did not open his arms to his frowned while standing. ("Zulm", 242 p.)

Human speech is a complex process, and a multifaceted phenomenon. Even in expressing the expressiveness of its giving these characteristics in a work of art and the clear appearance of

the process of the plot taking place, paralinguistic means have their place: - goes. Tell me where it is. You have no right to break the decision.

Matkobul remained to express with a handshake that this dağdag was not attached to the Yellow Jack. ("Kurort", 287 p.)

He had nothing to think of, his head was hollowed out and empty. Sadiqjan" ask for his condition and see what you know", in the sense that it is an eye for Ma'sumah tikdi. Ma ' suma sat like he did not notice, although he felt what purpose was hidden in this vision Zamiri. ("Qasos", 320 p.)

In the process of communication, the speaker has a certain goal in front of him when outlining his opinion. This goal will consist in the speaker's understanding, understanding of the listener. In this, the understanding and understanding of each other by the speaker and the listener is achieved only when there is a basis common to them: Daughter, peace? - asked Uncle Paulvon, when he had an eye-fight with his woman. ("Bekat", 363 p.)

Uncle Polvon said something in a low voice, but did not hear delicately. Uncle Paulvon bowed his head and birpas was silent (That book)

Sarvi could have said These things in the way of answers to Khalida's question. But she did not want to warn the girl about this secret." I don't know, " the shoulder snapped. ("Oqibatul - amr", 140 p.)

Paralinguistic means, in addition to clarifying the speech situation, are also of great importance in its compactness. Its use as part of speech is closely related to the tendency for economy, which is always practiced in the language. Mimic nonverbal means performed by the movements of the person in this place, through the movements of the face, eyes, eyebrows, tongue, torso, in many cases create the basis for the emergence of emotional relationships in the transmission of information to the addressee. In particular, the importance and role of the eye are extremely high. Especially in the content of an artistic text, such a mimic tool that comes not only expresses the impressionability of reality, but also serves to depict the emotional experiences of the hero in a clear state. That is why the eye is recognized as an organ that actively participates in the relationship of human speech communication. Various meanings in a work of art can be transmitted through the shortening, closing or large opening of the eyes:

He came to come , but from shame, his face burned and he took it towards the ground. Narzi, who was saying goodbye to his relatives, was often looking at him with a hopeful eye, as if waiting for something from Nozik. ("Bekat", 363 p.)

- *Peace, Uncle ... Hm ... haligi ... did not a letter come from my brother Nazrulla?*

After this question from dabdurust, the surprised couple looked at each other. (that book)

- *With the departure of the woman's ladder, uncle Colonel sewed a test on the girl:*

- *- Daughter, your eyes are telling your concerns. Do not hide. If you don't say it today, you will say it sooner or later. Is Narzi alive? Tell me the truth in your aunt's oil, let the public not hear it, the heart is chatter.*

- *- Although the slender Polvon took a look at the uncle, he sewed the song gaze into the vineyard and began to speak more often : they wrote me a letter... they said, "I will not go home..." Nozick's voice trembled. Uncle Paulvon stared at him with admiration:*

- *- Why? (that book 364 p.)*

Even from the above examples, the nonverbal means associated with the eye clearly and vividly show the use of multiple bora in our speech communication even with the use of words related to the dialect in the writer's fiction text. From the examples below, we see a

vivid depiction of the emotional experiences of the hero through paralinguistic factors associated with a single vision:

Exposing the young man's lie and not disgracing, he entered the House. But he did not walk towards the shelf, nor did he look. On the contrary, the half-open door went to the pan and stared at the young man in a stealthy way. (*"Nomus"*, 21 p.)

He was teased by a young man of low stature, with a swallow-moustache, who wore his white cap tilted. – Will you not come out of a fall, if not?

Rustam looked at the Eagle, realizing that he was famous. ("Tiriklik suvi", 200 p.)

In summary, paralinguistic means are the simplest, cost-effective means in expressing a particular thought (whether it be colloquial or artistic speech). At the same time it also helps to ensure the expressiveness of the work of art. When transporting a certain message, conveying it to the addressee, paralinguistic means always approach linguistic means, serving as an assistant in ensuring the accuracy and compactness of speech. It can even come in a temporary linguistic unit task, exchanging places with linguistic means in some places. It follows that in the process of learning some language, it is not enough to learn only from the structure of that language. After all, just as there is no language outside society and there is no society without language, the social essence of language and the most basic means of communication have always served humanity as a *beminnat*. Tohir Malik, the creator of *Benazir*, also created incomparable works that take their place in the hearts of readers by making the most of the services.

References:

1. Nurmonov N. A. O'zbek tilining paralingvistik vositalari. – Andijon. 1980 yil.
2. Nurmonov. N.A. Tanlangan asaralar, 3 jildlik. 1-jild. Toshkent, 2001-yil.
3. Muratova, N. B. (2021). DISKURS JARAYONIDA ADRESANT VA ADRESATNING NOLISONIY VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISHI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(11), 1197-1203.
4. Muratova N.B. MULOQOT JARAYONIDA PARALINGVISTIK VOSITALARNING O'RNI. CENTRAL ASIAN ACADEMIC JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH 2181-2489 N2, 2022.
5. T. Malik Doka ro'mol qachon quriydi. – Toshkent, 2021.
6. T. Malik "Iblis devori", - Toshkent, 2007.
7. Tohir Malik "Nomus", Toshkent, 2021.
8. Tohir Malik, Voy, Onajonim... Toshkent, 2019.